

Solitons in a Ring — a Theoretical Model for Pseudorotation ?

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The problem of a soliton (a twist or a kink) which has been confined to a ring, perhaps due to topological restraints or due to non-linearities in the dynamics of the ring has been investigated. The conditions for the existence of the soliton have been studied and a classical expression valid for the energy of the soliton is found. This expression is quite simple and one can write down the corresponding quantum mechanical energies. As a possible application, the case of the simple molecule cyclopentane is suggested.

The possible existence of the soliton in molecular dynamics and their importance in such problems have been the subject of a large number of investigations. For recent interesting applications (Refs. 1–3 may be seen). However, there seems to be hardly any study of a situation in which the soliton is confined to a ring. In the following, we study such a problem. This, we suggest can serve as a model for pseudorotation in the molecule cyclopentane, an interesting phenomenon, which has been known for a long time⁴. It might be a natural guess that the most symmetric planar cyclopentane molecule with D_{5h} symmetry would be the most stable one. However, it has been observed that cyclopentane and most of its derivatives prefer to be in one of the two extremes, viz. envelope and half-chair or in any other conformation in between these two. In these two conformations the planar symmetry D_{5h} is reduced to C_s or C_2 respectively, for the instantaneous planar C–C framework. In the envelope conformation there is a symmetry plane perpendicular to the average plane of the cyclopentane ring and hence its molecular point group is C_s where the molecule resembles an open envelope whose flap is pointing upward. On the other hand, the half-chair form belongs to C_2 point group because of the presence of the C_2 axis in the molecular plane. The name half-chair has been given owing to its similarity with the rigid chair form of cyclohexane having local tetrahedral symmetry around each carbon atom. The C–C–C dihedral angles are slightly different in chair and half-chair forms. It has been rather established⁴ that the singleton out-of-plane position in envelope conformation would be assumed by all the

five carbon atoms in succession through the rotation of the puckering around the ring, popularly known as pseudorotation. The complicated motion of two out-of-plane ring vibrations in cyclopentane where the barrier height to planarity is large can be simulated⁴ as a superposition of two relatively simpler motions, viz. a pseudorotation and a radial vibration. Pseudorotation refers to the motion of the maximum amplitude of the puckering around the cyclopentane ring while the radial vibration is the nearly harmonic oscillation of the amount of puckering around an equilibrium value. In 1965, the pseudorotation vibration in tetrahydrofuran was evidenced⁵ spectroscopically. This work has been followed^{4,6} by gas-phase infrared Raman studies on several molecules exhibiting free as well as barrier to pseudorotation. A somewhat related study has been carried out⁷ on infinite polymeric chains which are cyclic within Born-Von Karman approximation.

We first study a model problem, in which we consider a sine-Gordon field with the topology of a ring. It may be noted that the sine-Gordon field has been considered here because it is simple and well-studied. This continuum model of a kink in a ring may not be very well suited for the discrete five site model of cyclopentane. A discrete structure like Toda lattice in terms of exponential interactions may be a somewhat better choice. It may be helpful in distinguishing different atomic sites which in turn would allow one to differentiate between pseudorotation in different molecules, for example cyclopentane and furan. The field ϕ obeys the equation.

$$\phi_{xx} - \phi_{tt} - \sin \phi = 0 \tag{1}$$

with the periodic boundary condition

$$\phi(x, t) = \phi(x + 2\pi, t) \tag{2}$$

where x and t are spatial and temporal variables respectively. To find the solitonic solution we adopt the usual trick and put $\phi(x, t) = \phi(s)$ where

$$s = x - \omega t \tag{3}$$

into equation (1). ω is the angular velocity with which the soliton moves around the ring. Then

$$\frac{d^2\phi(s)}{ds^2} (\omega^2 - 1) + \sin \phi = 0 \tag{4}$$

and

$$\phi(s + 2\pi) = \phi(s) \tag{5}$$

It is convenient to define a new variable τ by $\tau = \int (\omega^2 - 1)^{1/2} ds = v s$

Then equations (4) and (5) become

$$\phi_{\tau\tau} + \sin \phi(\tau) = 0 \tag{6}$$

$\phi(\tau)$ would have to satisfy

$$\phi(\tau + 2\pi v) = \phi(\tau) \tag{7}$$

Equation (6) is the equation for a simple pendulum which can be easily realised by writing it as

$$\phi_{\tau\tau} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial\phi} \{I(\phi)\} \tag{8}$$

where $I(\phi) = 1 - \cos \phi \tag{9}$

One can think of equation (8) as the Newton's equation of motion for a particle moving in the periodic potential given by equation (9). It may be noted that thinking in terms of such a particle is only a convenience, and that this particle has no physical existence. If the energy E_p of the particle is greater than 2 then the motion is unbounded and no solution of the form $\phi(s)$ satisfying the boundary condition (5) is possible. However, if the energy of the particle is less than 2 then the motion can be periodic.

That is, it obeys

$$\phi(\tau + I) = \phi(\tau) \tag{10}$$

I is the period and is determined by the energy E_p of the particle. Comparing equations (7) and (10) we realise that we are interested in solutions that satisfy $I = 2\pi v$. The period I can be determined by solving the equation (8). From this we get

$$\phi_{\tau}^2/2 + V(\phi) = E_p \tag{11}$$

This equation is nothing but a statement of the conservation of energy of the particle. As our interest is only with $E_p < 2$ we define ϕ_0 by

$$E_p = 1 - \cos \phi_0 \tag{12}$$

with ϕ_0 lying in the range $(0, \pi)$. Then

$$\phi_{\tau}^2 = 2(\cos \phi - \cos \phi_0)$$

or $d\phi \{2(\cos \phi - \cos \phi_0)\}^{1/2} = d\tau \tag{13}$

We choose τ such that $\tau = 0$ implies $\phi = 0$. Then

$$\int_0^{\phi} \frac{d\phi}{\{2(\cos \phi - \cos \phi_0)\}^{1/2}} = \tau \tag{14}$$

That is

$$I(\epsilon, k) = \tau \tag{15}$$

In equation (15), $F(\epsilon, k)$ is the incomplete elliptic integral of the first kind. For a definition of this formula 290.00 of Byrd and Friedman⁸ may be seen. In our case $\epsilon = \sin^{-1}(\sin(\phi/2)/k)$ and $k = \sin(\phi_0/2)$. Defining the period of oscillation as four times the time needed for ϕ to increase from 0 to ϕ_0 , we obtain

$$I = 4F(\pi/2, k) = 4K(k) \tag{16}$$

$K(k)$ is the complete elliptic integral of the first kind (formula 110.06 may be seen⁸). This equation gives k as a function of ω the angular velocity of the soliton. As ϕ_0 varies between 0 and π , K varies between $\pi/2$ and ∞ monotonically. So equation (15) has only one solution for a given $v > 1$. That is, to have a soliton-like solution $\omega^2 < 2$. Equation (16) gives k as a function of ω . Writing this as $K(k) = \pi v/2$ and using the result 122.10 of Byrd and Friedman, we obtain

$$k^2 = 1 - dn^4(\pi v/4) \tag{17}$$

where $dn(x)$ is a Jacobian elliptic function. The energy E_p of the particle is given by $E_p = 2k^2$. So we now have an expression for E_p in terms of the angular velocity of the soliton.

It may be noted that our treatment is not yet quantum mechanical. In order to quantise our model, we adopt a very simplistic approach. We first calculate the energy of the field configuration, classically, in the case where a soliton exists in the ring. This energy is given by

$$\mathcal{E}[\phi] = \int_0^{2\pi} ds ((\phi_s^2 + \phi_t^2) / 2 + V(\phi)) \quad (18)$$

using $\phi(x, t) = \phi(x - \omega t)$, we obtain

$$\mathcal{E}[\phi] = \int_0^{2\pi} ds (\phi_s^2 (\omega^2 + 1) / 2 + V(\phi)) \quad (19)$$

But from the equation (11),

$$\phi_s^2 / (2\nu^2) + V(\phi) = E_p \quad (20)$$

Eliminating ϕ_s^2 using this equation, we obtain

$$\mathcal{E}[\phi] = \int_0^{2\pi} ds \left[(\omega^2 + 1) \nu^2 (E_p - V(\phi)) + V(\phi) \right] \quad (21)$$

On putting $E_p = 2k^2$ and $V(\phi) = (1 - \cos \phi) = 2k^2 sn^2(\tau)$ (formula 120.01 may be seen⁸) where sn is the sine amplitude function, we can perform the integral in equation (21) using the formula 310.02 of Ref 8. This gives

$$\mathcal{E}[\phi] = 4\pi - 4\pi\nu^2(\omega^2 + 1)dn^4(\pi\nu/4) + 4\nu(E(2\pi\nu) - E(0)) \quad (22)$$

In equation (22), $E(u)$ denotes the incomplete elliptic integral of the second kind

Let us define the momentum conjugate to ω as

$$J = \partial \mathcal{E}(\omega) / \partial \omega \quad (23)$$

Considering $\mathcal{E}(\omega) = \mathcal{E}[\phi]$ and using 730.01 of Ref. 8, we can obtain $J = J(\omega)$ and in turn expand $J(\omega)$ as a Maclaurin's series in ω . The series can be inverted using the calculus of residues to obtain

$$\omega = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} J_n J^n \quad (24)$$

where

$$J_n = 1/n! \left[\frac{d^{n-1}}{d\omega^{n-1}} \left(\frac{\omega}{J(\omega)} \right)^n \right]_{\omega=0} \quad (25)$$

Therefore,

$$\mathcal{E}[\phi] = \mathcal{E}(\omega) = \mathcal{E} \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} J_n J^n \right) \quad (26)$$

Imposing the quantisation condition for J as

$$J_M = M\hbar, \quad M = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots \quad (27)$$

we have

$$\mathcal{E}_M[\phi] = \mathcal{E} \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} J_n (M\hbar)^n \right) \quad (28)$$

Spectral transitions among these energy levels may be studied using the selection rule^{4,9} in infrared domain as $\Delta M = \pm 2$ and for the corresponding Raman transitions as $\Delta M = 0$. It should be emphasised that the pseudorotational combination bands⁴ or the ir subband structure⁴ in cyclopentane would reveal themselves depending on how close the energy levels given by equation (28) would be to the true pseudorotation vibrational energy levels⁴ of cyclopentane or its derivatives. It is expected that it would be able to reproduce in 1-D, the quadratic spacing⁴ in these energy levels as well as the barrier to the planarity⁴. It may, however, be noted that many things remain to be done before this model would be able¹⁰ to reproduce the true quantum mechanical picture.

Thus, we have shown that the topological mapping between the pseudorotation of the puckering around the cyclopentane ring and the rotational motion of the soliton may provide additional insights into the former.

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